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SILK FIBROIN- APPLICATIONS IN MEDICAL TEXTILE

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ABSTRACT

The skin is the largest organ of the human body, protecting it from the external environment. Despite their strong self-regeneration capability, severe skin abnormalities do not heal on their own and must be covered with skin substitutes. Silk fibroin has the potential to be used in tissue engineering. We discuss our opinion of its utility as a biomaterial for tissue reconstruction in diverse organs, with a particular emphasis on wound healing. We cover the various methods for preparing regenerated silk fibroin, as well as their benefits and drawbacks, in addition to the key scaffold systems for wound management. We conclude that fibroin is a promising choice for further research due to its strength, structural flexibility, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and potential for modification.

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INTRODUCTION

Skin is the largest organ of the body and its prime function is the protection of the body from the external environment. Skin wounds are damage to normal skin composition. It can be either an acute wound resulting from an incision or physical trauma or a chronic wound like a diabetic foot ulcer, pressure ulcer, burn, ischemic wound, etc. The process of wound healing is essential to prevent pathogens attack on the damaged tissue and reconstruct the damaged tissue partially or wholly. Although skin has self-healing potential, defects measuring more than a certain diameter will not heal spontaneously and require some skin substitutes.

Generally, wound healing has four stages ie; haemostasis, inflammation, cell proliferation, and remodelling. The primary principle of wound healing management is the use of appropriate wound dressing material. Modern wound dressings are aimed to cover wounds and provide a barrier against bacterial penetration.[1]

Due to their low cost, distinctive physical and chemical features, drug-eluting textiles have recently received a lot of attention for usage in various applications. Natural or synthetic fibers can be used to make textiles. Cotton, silk, keratin, and flax are the natural fibres that are most frequently utilised in medical textiles.[2]

Textile candidates with biomedical application

A. Cotton

Cotton fabric is often used as a hemostatic bandage due to its low skin irritation, softness, and breathability.[3] Cotton gauze was invented in 1891.[4] Its ability to absorb water from the blood quickly allows it to concentrate platelets, erythrocytes, and clotting factors.[5]

However, gauze dressings are incapable of maintaining a moist wound environment, which may result in eschar formation. At the same time, gauze wound dressings are less effective than semiocclusive wound dressings at providing an effective barrier against microbial invasion into the wound. Since gauze wound dressings cannot handle wound exudate properly, they must be changed frequently, resulting in painful removal and patient discomfort.[6]

Recently, some researchers attempted to assess the thermo-physiological comfort qualities of surgical cotton gauze coated with chitosan and its efficiency for bacterial colonisation prevention. The results show that the functionalized medical gauze can produce low friction on the wound bed, allowing for a high absorption capacity of wound exudates and a fair degree of moisture.[7]

B. Keratin

Keratin is a family of cysteine-rich filament-forming proteins. It is the primary component of hair, wool, hooves, nails, feathers, and horns.[8] Keratins and keratinous materials are classified into two types based on their secondary protein structures: α -keratin and β -keratin. It should be remembered that the expression of different keratins varies depending on the stage of the wound healing process because each of them has different functions to play in the process.[9]

Keratin biomaterials do have a distinct set of properties, including high biocompatibility, biodegradability, and bioactivity. They also have a hydrophilic surface, which many synthetic polymers lack.[10] Keratin biomaterials manufactured from wool and hair have proven the capacity to facilitate cellular attachment due to cell-binding motifs such as glutamic acid-aspartic acid-serine (EDS), arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (RGD), and leucine-aspartic acid-valine (LDV).[11]

Keratin has antimicrobial activity, although it is not as strong as that silver nanoparticle. This could be related to the high content of cysteine residues, which aid in the binding of keratin's positively charged amino groups to the negatively charged bacterial cell wall, causing keratin to prevent bacterial growth.[12] Konop et al. reported in vitro antibacterial activities of an insoluble fraction of keratin scaffolds alone or with the inclusion of silver nanoparticles against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Moreover, they find no signs of bacterial infection in diabetic mice's keratin-treated wounds.[13]

The major limitation of keratin biomaterials is their low mechanical strength; thus, natural or synthetic polymers were carefully incorporated to optimize the physical properties.[14,15]

C. Flax

Flax (*Linum usitatissimum*) was one of the first plants to be extracted, spun, and woven into textiles.[16] Flax fibres are derived from the stems of the flax plant and are composed of cellulose with a more crystalline structure than cotton, making the fibres stiffer and more rigid. It has a tensile strength of 800-1500 MPa and hydrophilic characteristics, while moisture absorption impacts mechanical qualities; stiffness and strength both decrease as the fibre swells.[2]

Because of their biocompatibility, they are being explored in tissue engineering. In-vitro tests have shown that silver-nanoparticle-coated linen fabric has high antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, which, when paired with its hydrophilic qualities, makes it a competitive candidate for use in wound dressings.[17]

D. Silk

Silk is the most commonly used textile component, and it is sourced from a wide range of organisms including spiders, silkworms, scorpions, mites, and flies. Silkworms are a good source for the clinical field because of their outstanding biocompatibility, acceptable mechanical characteristics, and bulk production in the textile industry.[18]

Silk is composed of two proteins: sericin(SS) and fibroin(SF). Glycoprotein in silk cocoons consists of 30% hydrophilic sericin and 70% hydrophobic fibroin. Sericin is a gummy protective covering that coats the double-stranded fibroin to give the silk structural stability.[19] Silk produced from both mulberry (domestic) and non-mulberry (wild) silkworms has distinct properties.

Table No:1 Comparison Between Mulberry And Non-mulberry Silk.

Properties	Mulberry silk	Non-mulberry silk
Source	<i>Bombyx mori</i> . [20]	<i>Antheraea mylitta</i> , <i>A. assama</i> , <i>A. roylei</i> , <i>A. frithi</i> , <i>A. pernyi</i> , <i>A. yamamai</i> and <i>Philosamia ricini</i> . [20]
Structure	Silk fibroin possesses a heavy (H) chain, light (L) chain and P25 glycoprotein in a 6:6:1 ratio. [20]	Silk fibroin lacks both L-chain and the P25 glycoprotein. [20]
Tensile strength (GPA)	4.3 ±5.2 [20]	1.9-4.5 [20]
%elongation	10-23.4 [20]	4-39 [20]
Hydrophobic behaviour	Less hydrophobic. [20]	More hydrophobic due to rich (-Ala-)n polypeptide sequences. [20]
Molecular weight	Fibroin-25-350kDa. [20] Sericin- 20-400kDa. [20]	<i>Antheraea mylitta</i> -197-395kDa <i>A. assama</i> -20-220kDa <i>P. ricini</i> -45-97kDa [20] <i>Antheraea mylitta</i> -30 to more than 300kDa <i>A. assama</i> -66kDa <i>P. ricini</i> -66kDa [20]
FTIR spectra of silk protein	1620 cm ⁻¹ - amide I (C=O stretching) 1513 cm ⁻¹ - amide II (N-H bending) 1230 and 1444 cm ⁻¹ - amide III (C-N stretching) 694 cm ⁻¹ - amide IV. [21]	No difference in spectra. [22]
Solvent for dissolution	LiBr, Ajisawas solvent, Formic acid:CaCl ₂ , Ca(NO ₃) ₂ , LiSCN, choline hydroxide, ZnCl ₂ etc. [20]	Ca(NO ₃) ₂ and LiSCN are preferred for dissolution because poly(-Ala-) β-sheets make non-mulberry silk fibroin more resistant to dissolution. [20]

Bombyx mori silk fibroin

Silk fibroin consists of a light (L) chain polypeptide (26kDa) and a heavy (H) chain polypeptide (390 kDa molecular weight) joined by a single disulphide bond at the C-terminus of the H-chain, resulting in H - L complex. [23,24] The heavy chain is made up of 12 hydrophobic domains and 11 hydrophilic domains. Hydrophobic domains have amino acids in a repetitive sequence, whereas the amino acids in the hydrophilic domains are non-repetitive. [25]

The repetitive domains contain glycine, alanine, and serine, as well as tyrosine, valine, and threonine. They can assemble themselves into β sheets by intramolecular or intermolecular forces like hydrogen bonds and Vander Waals forces, resulting in the formation of highly organised crystalline areas in silk fibroin. Non-repetitive domains containing charged / acidic amino acids, such as glutamic acid, aspartic acid, arginine, and lysine create a semi-amorphous area in silk fibroin. [26]

Silk fibroin can exist in three conformational structures: silk I, II, and III. Silk I is a water-soluble metastable form composed of α sheets and random coil confirmation, whereas silk II is a water-insoluble form composed of extended β sheets. Silk III has a helical structure that can only be seen at the air-water interface. [27,28]

The life cycle of the silkworm [29]

Sericulture is the term for the cultivation of silk worms. Throughout its lifespan, the mulberry silk moth goes through many phases (egg, larva, pupa, and moth). The flowchart below depicts the different stages in the life cycle of a silk moth.

Figure No:1 Life Cycle Of Silk Worm.

A cocoon is comprised of a single continuous silk strand that is 500-1200m long.[29]

Although both SF and SS function well in cell proliferation tests, sericin induces inflammatory reactions due to elevated immunoglobulin E (IgE), leading to type I hypersensitivity reaction as well as a delayed hypersensitivity reaction causing an asthma in certain individuals.[30]

A prospective cohort study in India found that employees were extremely sensitive to silk filature. Silk allergen sensitivity was determined using a skin prick test; of the 120 subjects who were exposed to SS, 35 (29.17%) were sensitive to it. The same skin prick test was performed on 64 children under the age of 15 in a case study by Wen et al. It was observed that 75% of them showed an increase in IgE levels, as well as symptoms of a delayed hypersensitivity reaction, such as allergic rhinitis and conjunctivitis.[30,31] An inflammatory response is seen only when SS is physically associated with the core fibroin fibres. Therefore either sericin or silk fibroin is taken for the manufacturing of biomaterials.[32]

Silk fibroin is the most commonly used fibre for wound dressing applications. Fibroin is insoluble in water because of the large concentration of hydrophobic amino acid residues on its surface and in its bulk, such as alanine.[33] To properly disperse the SF, the dense fibrous structure must be swollen, and the hydrogen bond network must break down, resulting in the total dispersion of individual fibroin molecules.[34] Biomaterials of silk fibroin can be prepared by using silk fibroin solution or by using grounded silk fibroin.[35].

Figure no:2 silk based formulation.

A. Silk fibroin solution

Degumming and dissolution are two important processes in the development of water-soluble silk fibroin. When coupled with fibroin, sericin becomes a poisonous substance that causes inflammation; also, the degummed fibres are insoluble in water due to the gummy nature of sericin. Degumming is accomplished in textile companies using boiling water or detergent solutions, but it has also been performed in laboratories using various chemical agents such as carbonate solutions, urea, and sodium lauryl sulphate. To assist in the elimination of sericin from the fibres, all the degumming procedures use denaturants (heat and pH).[36].

Figure No:3 Processing Steps And The Reagents To Obtain Silk Fibroin Solution.

Table No:2 Advantages And Disadvantages Of Degumming Solvents.

Various agents	degumming	Temperature	Time (min)	Advantages	Disadvantages
0.02 M Na ₂ CO ₃ [37]		80°C	40-60	Easily available. Low cost. Silk has higher whiteness.[38]	Largest decrease in elasticity and yield point. Due to strong alkalinity, the silk fibroin degraded to a small molecular weight.[39] A large volume of wastewater pollutes the ecosystem.[40]
8 mol/l urea (99%) at pH 9.0[39]		80°C	15	Less damage to silk fibre.[38]	Urea buffer usually contains a high concentration of urea. β-mercaptoethanol is a harmful reagent and a vital component of the urea degumming buffer making it unsuitable for industrial manufacturing.[40]
0.2 mol/l boracic acid (99.5%.) in a 0.05 mol/l sodium borate (99.5%) buffer at pH 9.0[39]		98°C	90	Borate buffer degumming is better than urea and Na ₂ CO ₃ in terms of the mechanical properties of silk fibroin.[39]	
Enzymatic degumming using trypsin and bromelain.[39]		37°C	120min	High efficiency. Mild reaction. Strong specificity. Low pollution.[38]	High cost.[38]

Silk fibroins are insoluble in water and most organic solvents after extraction from *Bombyx mori*. Concentrated acid solutions, as well as concentrated aqueous, organic, and aqueous-organic salt solutions, dissolve silk fibroin.[28]The β-sheet structure of silk fibre would primarily change to a random coil when treated with these types of solvents due to the strong hydration of the concentrated solution and the ability of alkali ions to bind with tyrosine residues in fibroin, resulting in disruption of the Vander Waals force and hydrogen bonds in fibroin molecules. The fibroin would swell and then dissolve as a result of this. Furthermore, a mixture of alcohols such as ethanol or methanol with an aqueous salt solution may improve fibroin solubility.[41]

Dialysis is a rate-limiting step required to remove salts or ions from silk fibroin solutions to decrease cytotoxicity.[42]After dialysis, protein concentration was determined using the Bradford standard test. The fibroin solution was blended with the Bradford reagent for 5 minutes before measuring the absorbance at 595 nm. The Bradford test is based on the dye Coomassie Blue G-250 binding to protein. In the test, bovine serum albumin was employed as a standard protein.[37]

Dissolution methods

Ternary solvent system

To dissolve silk fibres, various salt ternary systems have been used, the most common of which is the Ajisawas solvent system. Purified fibroin (10 g) was dissolved completely in 100 mL of the ajisawas solvent (CaCl₂-CH₃CH₂OH-H₂O 1:2:8 mol ratio).Following that, dialysis is performed for three days at room temperature using a dialysis cassette with a six-times of water change. To get rid of the undissolved particles, the solution is then centrifuged at 6,000 rpm.[43]

The main drawback of this method is the tendency to aggregate during dialysis; however, this can be avoided by using stepwise decreases of urea during dialysis, which can eliminate the need for high-speed centrifugation and significantly improve silk yields.[44]

Based on their ability to dissolve silk fibre, Pilanee Vaithanomsat and Chidchai Punyasawon (2006) conducted a comparison study of various solvent systems. The solvents used were $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2/\text{ethanol}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CaCl}_2/\text{ethanol}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MgCl}_2/\text{ethanol}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{ZnCl}_2/\text{ethanol}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, with a salt:ethanol:water mole ratio of 1:2:8. According to the study results, out of all the solvent systems tested, the one comprising MgCl_2 , ethanol, and water at a mole ratio of 0.8:2:8 performed the best at totally dissolving the silk cocoon because it could penetrate the fibres of the silk and alter their structure.[41]

Lithium bromide (LiBr)

1 gm of degummed silk was dissolved in 5 ml of a 9.3 M LiBr solution at 70°C for 3 hours to make a silk fibroin solution.[37] According to research, residual lithium ions in silk fibroin cause skin and eye irritation and are dangerous if eaten. So dialysis is necessary. To ensure the removal of lithium ions conductivity test is carried out before and after dialysis.[42]

The LiBr must be added to the silk rather than the silk being added to the LiBr so that, the silk will eventually be covered and dissolved by the LiBr. Avoid shearing the solution whenever feasible to avoid the induction of β sheet within the silk.[45]

Qin Wang et al. (2012) examined the effect of various dissolving solvents on the degradation of silk fibroin, including 52% w NaSCN aqueous solution, 9.3M LiBr, and ajisawas solvent, and concluded that LiBr- H_2O and NaSCN appeared to be milder than $\text{CaCl}_2\text{-EtOH-H}_2\text{O}$ because $\text{CaCl}_2\text{-EtOH-H}_2\text{O}$ caused greater degradation of the heavy chain of fibroin than other solvents.[46].

Formic acid- calcium chloride solution

Silk fibroin is not readily soluble in formic acid (FA), although regenerated SF materials are. Silk fibroin, on the other hand, can dissolve readily in an FA complex solution including CaCl_2 , LiBr, phosphoric acid, or hydroxyapatite.[40]

To make an SF solution, dried degummed silk was dissolved in $\text{CaCl}_2\text{-FA}$ for 3 hours at room temperature with CaCl_2 concentrations varying from 1-12% (w/v). Silk fibroin solubility rises with increasing CaCl_2 concentrations. The dialysis process mentioned in the previous methods to remove ions can be avoided by simply placing the obtained silk fibroin scaffolds in deionised water for a few hours. The resultant solution appeared stable at ambient temperature for at least 24 hours, demonstrating that wet spinning can be employed to generate nanofibers. In the $\text{CaCl}_2\text{-FA}$ solution, silk collapsed into nanofibrils rather than individual molecules.[47]

According to another study, the dissolution of silk and the shape of nanofibrils were highly dependent on CaCl_2 concentration. $\text{CaCl}_2\text{-FA}$ was sorbed into nanofibrils and inflated the fibrils. As a consequence, the nanofibril β sheet was momentarily changed into random coils without collapsing the nanofibril structure.[48]

Zinc chloride solvent

Degummed silk fibres were incubated for 1 hour at 45°C in a 56% (w/w) aqueous ZnCl_2 solution (1:100 silk to solvent ratio), yielding a 1% (w/v) silk fibroin solution. Gel filtration was used to desalt. Organic and other solvents that dissolve or otherwise affect the integrity of dialysis membranes are highly compatible with gel filtration. Dialysis membranes constructed of cellulose, for example, can dissolve in ZnCl_2 solutions with concentrations ranging from 60-70% (w/w). The main drawback of this method is the cost of gel filtration, although it minimises the time and rate of deterioration of the silk fibres.[49]

Ionic liquid system

Ionic liquids are becoming more popular as alternate solvents for increasing the solubility of different compounds while preserving their chemical characteristics.[50] Because of their potential to break hydrogen bonds between β -sheet structures, ionic liquids are a novel form of solvent that can dissolve silk fibroin. Ionic liquids fall into three categories: Ionic liquids based on 3-methyl imidazolium-based ionic liquids, protic ionic liquids, and choline salts. Ionic liquids reduce the need for harmful organic volatile liquids, which are required for regenerated silk dissolution.[51,52]

Eventhough, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride (BMIM-Cl) has been shown to completely dissolve silk, the high melting point of BMIM-Cl makes processing difficult, whereas it has been observed that the properties of silk fibroin change with temperature, and that over a certain temperature i.e ; 90°C , the silk begins to degrade and the amount recovered is very low.[53]

Meanwhile, choline hydroxide, a biocompatible liquid derived from lecithin, has several advantages, such as shortening processing time and temperature, and hence the destruction of silk. Dialysis can be eliminated from the method by using ionic solutions.[54]

To obtain 25% of the silk fibre solution, degummed silk fibres were dissolved in choline-based ionic liquid for 2 hours at 50°C and 200 rpm stirring speed. The solution was then placed into methanol (an anti-solvent) to precipitate the silk powder, which had been centrifuged to separate the silk powder and the methanol fraction containing the ionic liquid. The methanol in the solution was evaporated with a rotary evaporator to obtain the ionic liquid for the next cycle of silk powder extraction from silk fibroin fibre. Even after three rounds of dissolution, the recycled solvent has the same dissolution capacity. Finally, this process has the benefit of extracting the silk fibroin in nanosized powders that can be used to produce various silk-based scaffolds.[54]

Although this approach streamlines the silk fibroin regeneration process, it has significant disadvantages. To begin with, ionic liquids are quite costly. Second, it takes a long time for silk fibroin to dissolve in ionic liquids. In most cases, it takes two hours of continuous stirring for SF fibres to completely dissolve in ionic solutions.[53,54]

Grounded silk fibroin

Degummed silk fibroin is powdered, and fibroin suspension is made by putting it through a grinder with a spinning grinding stone at 1500 rpm four times. This suspension can be used to make scaffolds.[55]The film prepared from ground fibroin suspension has superior mechanical and thermal properties when compared to those prepared from regenerated fibroin solutions. Furthermore, the grinding procedure was discovered to be capable of micro-fibrillating fibroins while keeping their β -sheet structure and not dissolving them.[35]

Okahisa et al. evaluated the films (F_1 and F_2) made by using the traditional dissolution method (ajisawas solvent) and ground silk fibroin powder. The study concluded that the traditional method's film (F_1) had a silk I structure whereas, film prepared by using the new method (F_2) had a silk II (β sheet) structure. Furthermore, the elastic modulus of the F_2 was greater than that of the F_1 due to the lack of thermal damage to the fibril structure. Since GF can be generated easily and without the use of chemicals, this approach is likely to be used in a variety of sectors, including tissue engineering, where biocompatibility is necessary.[55]

Table No:3 Pros And Cons Of Solvents Used For Dissolution Of Silk Fibroin.

Solvents	Advantages	Disadvantage
LiBr-H ₂ O	Less dissolving time. Doesn't aggregate during dialysis.[56]	Expensive. Corrosive. Environmental pollution.[56]
Ajisawas solvent	Cheaper than LiBr salt. Non toxic.[56]	Aggregate during dialysis. Takes too much time to dissolve SF .[56] SF undergoes molecular degradation.[57]
Formic acid-CaCl ₂	No dialysis.[47]	Formic acid is highly volatile.[58]
ZnCl ₂	No dialysis.[49]	Costly due to the gel filtration technique.[49]
Ionic liquids	No dialysis. Less degradation.[54] Nontoxic solvents.[52]	Expensive.[54] Takes more time for dissolution.[53,54]

Storage of silk fibroin

The silk fibroin solution may be kept at 4°C for at least a month. Stored silk will ultimately gel, depending on its purity, however, gelation periods will vary. Utilizing a 10% w/v PEG solution, dialysis may be employed to concentrate the resulting regenerated silk fibroin solution. The concentrated silk solution will gel after a few days even if kept at 4°C. Once the solution has gelled, it can no longer be used for techniques that need a solution. The silk solution should be lyophilized if it is to be stored for more than one month. Thereby silk fibroin will stay stable at room temperature for years and can be reconstituted in Hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP).[45]

Silk fibroin applications in the medical field

Silk outperforms commonly used polymeric degradable biomaterials such as collagen and poly(L-lactic acid) (PLA) in terms of strength. B. mori silk fibres have an ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of 740 MPa. Collagen has a UTS of 0.9-7.4 MPa, while PLA has a UTS of 28-50 MPa. As a result, silk fibroin is an ideal polymer choice for biomedical applications. Silk fibroin is a biodegradable substance in addition to possessing excellent mechanical qualities. Highly crystallised silk degrades slowly, however, the rate in vivo is affected by the implantation site, mechanical environment, and features of the silk preparation process. Silk degradation enzymes include protease XIV, papain, α -chymotrypsin, matrix metalloproteinases-I and II and collagenase IA.[45,59,60]

Biocompatibility is an important aspect of scaffold implementation because it allows cells to adhere to the scaffold surface and migrate within the scaffold structure, where they can proliferate and differentiate. Furthermore, the scaffold must induce no or just minor immune reactions following implantation. Since its approval by the US Food and Drug Administration in 1993, SF has been widely utilised as a suture material. There is no noticeable macrophage response to SF membranes or fibres, according to in vitro and in vivo studies. Sakabe et al. observed no evidence of thrombus formation in their in vivo trials utilising fibroin-coated sutures placed in the animal connective tissue on days 1 and 14.[60]

a) Skeletal system

Since cells, fibres, collagen, and hydroxyapatite make up the majority of bone, the scaffolding material used to support bone tissues must guarantee matrix hardness and matrix deposition. Because of its excellent biocompatibility, high toughness, and mechanical strength, SF is a reasonable option. According to a study, SF scaffolds improve human mesenchymal stem cell-based repair of femoral defects in nude mice. It has been demonstrated that incorporating hydroxyapatite nanoparticles into silk matrix enhances bone regeneration in animals.[60]

b) Nervous system

The nervous system is made up of specialised cells that are organised in complicated networks and can integrate and assimilate signals from many tissues and organs. The neurological system, on the other hand, has a low regeneration capacity. Stem cell (SC) therapy is very popular, because of its pluripotency and multipotency, capacity to regulate conversion into neural lineages, and/or release of particular molecules that can promote endogenous neurogenesis and self-repairing processes.[61]

Tang-Schomer and colleagues selectively inhibited glial cancer cells using drug-loaded SF films containing Ara-C, a mitotic inhibitor. These SF films were put directly to the cortical brain surface to breach the blood-brain barrier (BBB), allowing chemotherapeutic drugs to be delivered to brain tumours. In this manner, tiny molecules were able to penetrate deep brain areas without causing any adverse consequences.[61]

Because of perfect elasticity, tensile strength, and tear strength, biodegradable and biocompatible qualities of silk may be used to form a conduit to link damaged nerves, fixing the two cut sides of the nerve and encouraging development.[61] In a study, silk fibroin composites with chitosan or poly (l- lactic acid cocaprolactone) were able to bridge a 10 mm long sciatic nerve injury in rats.[62,63]

Growth factors (GFs) are naturally occurring substances that may bind to cells and govern a variety of biological functions. They are heat-sensitive proteins having a limited half-life that is prone to proteolytic destruction. The decrease in GFs production substantially reduces the neuron's ability to regenerate. The incorporation of GFs into silk-based biomaterials has been associated with good results such as providing a continuous and regulated source of GFs, targeted administration for regeneration, and protection of the integrated GFs from enzymatic activity in the body.[61] Tony M. Dinis et al created a new multi-functionalized silk-based nanofibre system by combining Nerve Growth Factor (NGF) and Ciliary NeuroTrophic Factor (CNTF) to support and promote nerve regeneration in the peripheral nervous system (PNS). Because of the NGF, these biofunctionalized nanofibers caused a threefold increase in neurite length following their contact. The CNTF enhanced glial cell proliferation, alignment, and migration.[64]

c) Ocular system

SF has good environmental and thermal stability, as well as high light conduction efficiency and sterilizability by the three common procedures of ethylene oxide, autoclaving, or gamma irradiation makes the silk a viable choice for ophthalmological application. Silk's non-mammalian origin, along with the fact that it does not feed on mammalian blood, lowers the risk of mammalian disease transmission.[65]

A silk fibroin solution was tested in a trial for the treatment of dry eye syndrome using mouse models. In dry eyes, the silk fibroin boosted tear production while decreasing ocular surface irregularity. Furthermore, silk fibroin reduced corneal epithelial cell detachment and restored many conjunctival goblet cells. Silk fibroin has also shown an anti-inflammatory effect by suppressing the release of inflammatory factors by the lacrimal glands. To sum up, silk fibroin is a promising novel medication with high effectiveness in treating inflammation and stabilising the tear film in dry eye syndrome.[66]

Despite its tunable mechanical strength, transparency, high light conduction efficiency, and sterilizability, silk fibroin is not extensively employed in the manufacture of contact lenses due to its lower oxygen permeability than daily wear contact lenses. With such poor oxygen permeability, adequate oxygen cannot reach the ocular surface and ensure proper corneal metabolism while using contact lenses.[67]

d) Wound care

Current commercially available wound dressing materials have various limitations, including inadequate mechanical strength, high cost, collagen invariability, low processability, limited availability and non-biodegradability. Therefore, SF could be considered an exceptional wound healing material owing to its abundance, intrinsic biodegradability, biocompatibility, mechanical robustness, good water and oxygen uptake, and low immunogenicity.[68]

In addition to the features listed above, SF promotes healing through more complex mechanisms and signalling pathways, which have been briefly summarised here. SF improves wound healing by promoting angiogenesis [69,70] and suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokine overexpression in wounds.[71] According to one study, NF- κ B signalling genes involved in cell proliferation, adhesion, inflammation, and the removal of reactive oxygen species were found to be strongly expressed in silk fibroin-treated cells.[72] SF also aids in the regulation of TGF- β_1 [71] and the faster production of collagen in a way similar to normal skin, resulting in scar-free skin.[73]

The authors found that silk fibroin films were better at healing cuts on the back of New Zealand rabbits than standard dressings. Histological analysis also showed successful reconstruction of the epidermis in the silk fibroin-treated samples. The authors used a quantitative method to measure wound healing in the untreated and fibroblast-treated groups of rabbits. After 10 days of treatment, the wound size in the silk fibroin-treated rabbits was reduced by 30% compared to the untreated rabbits, and it was reduced further by 11% after 15 days.[74]

The mechanical properties of silk scaffolds can help to stimulate the differentiation of cells into endothelial cells and neovascularization, even without the use of growth factors.[75]

Wound dressings containing antimicrobial agents have recently become an attractive solution for reducing the risk of infection and improving the healing process. Chan et al. created a nonwoven mat with antibacterial and anti-inflammatory characteristics using silk fibroin and a Chinese herbal extract.[76]

Some scientists proposed promising combinations of silk fibroin and silver nanoparticles for producing wound dressings that would prevent wound infection while also aiding wound healing. For instance, Pei et al. developed sponges of a silk fibroin/carboxymethylchitosan composite doped with silver nanoparticles and showed antibacterial efficacy against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*), as well as increased water absorption and transmission rate.[77]

Dhas et al. created silk fibres that were functionalized with silver nanocolloids and showed better thermal and mechanical properties as well as antibacterial activities against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* without harming fibroblasts.[78]

Miguel et al. used electrospinning to build multilayer asymmetric membranes that resembled both the dermis and the epidermis. The top layer comprised silk fibroin and poly (caprolactone), while the bottom layer was fibroin and hyaluronic acid infused with thymol as a herbal drug. The analysis showed biocompatibility, wettability, and mechanical properties that are suitable for wound healing applications.[79]

Wound dressing matrices are often supplied with growth factors to encourage epithelization in addition to antibacterial drugs to prevent infection. Schneider et al. examined the wound healing capabilities of EGF-loaded electrospun silk mats on human skin-equivalent models. The wound closure percentage of the EGF-silk mat was 98.5% after 48 hours, compared to 8.9% and 26.3% for the control and silk-only groups, respectively. The burst release of EGF from the surface of silk nanofibers assisted to reepithelialize the human skin model.[68]

Zhang et al. performed a major *in vivo* investigation of the effect of silk fibroin films on full-thickness skin defects. The capacity of the fibroin devices to shorten average wound healing time in rabbits was proven by the authors, and this was validated in the porcine model. Finally, a randomised, single-blind clinical trial on 71 patients indicated that silk fibroin films were effective in reducing both wound healing time and adverse effects when compared to commercial dressings. Those treated with fibroin healed completely in 14 days, but patients treated with control wound dressings healed in 19 days. According to scientists, the clinical use of silk fibroin films might be a better choice for wound care treatment.[80]

Multicomponent SF-based composite systems have recently received a lot of attention. For the treatment of chronic diabetic wounds, insulin-loaded SF microspheres encapsulated within SF sponges have been reported. In streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats, the released insulin was able to preserve its bioactivity while also accelerating *in vivo* wound healing by boosting vascularization via encouraging endothelial cell viability.[68]

Regenerated silk morphologies for wound management

A. Silk microspheres

Silk microspheres are capable of encapsulating and releasing growth factors, tiny molecules, or pharmaceutical drugs. One method of manufacturing microspheres involves an unsaturated fatty acid lipid (1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine) (DOPC) to encapsulate aqueous-based-silk solutions with a compound of interest. Once the vesicles are formed, the lipid is removed and the microspheres can be resuspended whenever needed. This process produces spheres with an average particle size of around 2 μm , which may be measured using optical microscopy or SEM.[45]

The second method employs the phase separation of silk and another polymer (e.g., polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)) to produce silk microspheres with sizes ranging from 300 nm to 20 μm . The second approach is easy and does not need the use of organic solvents. To encapsulate drugs in these spheres, add the medication to the silk solution before mixing it with the PVA. Several methods were used to analyze these spheres, including dynamic light scattering to estimate the size of the nanometer spheres, laser light diffraction to assess the size of the microspheres, and SEM to picture the morphology. The diffusion of drug molecules from a degraded polymeric matrix is the most common drug-release mechanism of microspheres.[45]

One of the most severe problems in the manufacturing of SF microspheres is the high molecular weight and protein nature of SF. Furthermore, when subjected to heat, salt, pH change, and strong shear, the SF self-assembles into fibres or gels.[40]

Qu J et al created basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) loaded silk fibroin (SF) microspheres using high-voltage electrostatic differentiation and lyophilization. These porous microspheres are having particle sizes ranging from 95 to 260 μm . The embedded bFGF demonstrated a slow release mode for more than 13 days without undergoing burst release, greatly encouraging cell proliferation in mouse embryonic lung fibroblast cells (L929 culture) compared to bFGF-unloaded cells.[81]

B. Silk Nanoparticles

Nanoparticles can effectively control drug release and targeting while preserving the activity and avoiding adverse effects. By adding SF solution dropwise to acetone, SF nanoparticles may be easily generated, and pharmaceuticals can be loaded during the production of SF nanoparticles. As certain medications are incompatible with acetone, they can be loaded into nanoparticles by physical adsorption or coprecipitation.[40]

For example, celecoxib and curcumin are loaded into SF nanoparticles by dissolving them in acetone and used for the treatment of arthritis. Both of these compounds are very cytotoxic in their original state, but their cytotoxicity is significantly lowered when they are encapsulated in SF nanoparticles.[82]

C. Scaffold systems

Scaffolds are artificial or natural structures that are engineered to mimic real physiological tissues or organs and help to induce desirable cellular interactions to contribute toward the formation of new functional tissues or related medical purposes. There are various types of scaffold systems such as films, nanofibre mats, hydrogels, sponges etc.[83]

1) Silk fibroin Sponges

Silk sponges are versatile 3D scaffolding materials that can be used to integrate molecules of interest. Their 3D porous nature enables cell adhesion, proliferation, and migration, as well as the movement of nutrients and waste.[60] Sponge pores of various diameters can be created by salt leaching (porogen), gas foaming, or freeze-drying methods.[45]

Sponges are divided into aqueous-based sponges and HFIP-based sponges. The aqueous-based sponges have good interconnectivity between the pores and do not require an organic solvent. This could be useful if a bioactive compound is added to the silk matrix during the process of manufacturing. Smoother surfaces along the pores and improved mechanical strength are characteristics of HFIP-based sponges. Aqueous sponges degrade more quickly than HFIP sponges.[45]

2) Silk based hydrogels

Hydrogels are three-dimensional, water-swollen polymer networks.[45] The low mechanical qualities of traditional hydrogels, as well as their inability to match the native tissue microstructure, may limit their use for wound healing. Furthermore, conventional hydrogels can only provide a moist environment, whereas multifunctional hydrogels are one of the most promising materials for tissue regeneration, particularly wound healing applications, because of their elasticity similar to native tissue, ability to provide a moist environment and absorb wound exudates through porous structures, allowing for gaseous exchange to prevent anaerobic bacterial growth, and acting as a barrier to prevent infection. Certain benefits of injectable hydrogel includes their capacity to encapsulate bioactive molecules insitu and fill wound sites while adhering to the wounds.[84,85]

Silk hydrogels can be created using a variety of methods, including high temperature, sonication, high ionic strength, freeze gelation, vortexing, direct electrical current application, or pH reduction.[45] The SF undergoes structural changes during the gelation process, transitioning from a disordered state to a β -sheet conformation, which physically cross-links and stabilises the gel.[60]

Recently, silk fibroin/hyaluronic acid hydrogels containing curcumin were made using the sonication method, and their antibacterial effectiveness against *S. aureus* was tested. The results show that the scaffold has low cytotoxicity, and high biocompatibility, and is successful in inhibiting microorganism growth.[86]

3) Silk fibroin films

To create SF films, the regenerated silk fibroin solution is loaded into the mould and then either air-dried or annealed with water or methanol. As previously stated, methanol can change the structure of regenerated silk fibroin from a high amount of α -helices (Silk I) to a predominantly β -sheet conformation (Silk II), and the concentration of alcohol influences the film's surface qualities. The fibroin film forms a jelly-like structure with a hydrated hydrogel as its outermost layer when treated with 80% methanol whereas, fibroin film treated with >90% ethanol has a tougher surface.[60]

Hofmann et al. described the use of methanol-treated SF films as controlled-release drug delivery depots. Increasing the crystallinity of SF resulted in a suppressed initial burst and extended release of different molecular weights of dextran, which was utilised as a model polysaccharide in that study.[68]

4) Silk fibroin nanofibre mats

Fibre spinning techniques such as electrospinning, wet spinning, and dry spinning are often used to create regenerated silk fibroin (RSF) mats or artificial silk fibres. *B. mori* fibroin is often dissolved in organic solvents such as formic acid, hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP), or hexafluoroacetone before being spun at voltages between 2 and 30 kV. With the help of this technique, non-woven mats with fibres varying in diameter from low nanometers to one micrometre have been created. Wet-spinning can be used to create micrometre-sized RSF fibres. Dry spinning, as opposed to wet spinning, does not require the use of organic solvents or coagulation baths, making it more environmentally friendly.[60]

The electrospinning technology can be used to create polymeric nanofibrous scaffolds that mimic the natural fibres of the extracellular matrix (ECM). The equipment required is simple, and the produced fibres are significantly smaller in diameter than normally spun fibres. Also this method allows for the incorporation of molecules of interest into the fibres. The fibres obtained will be less than 800 nm in diameter and appear quite uniform. SEM can be used to evaluate the morphology, diameter, and orientation of fibres.[45]

Apart from utilizing SF as nanoparticles, hydrogels, sponges, films, and fibres, considerable effort has been put into developing various types of SF-based biomaterials as drug delivery platforms. SF-based coatings, for example, are one of them. Bayraktar et al. applied an SF coating formulation directly to theophylline tablets. The coating was created by combining various PEG concentrations with 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylamino)-propyl carbodiimide-activated crosslinked SF. Regardless of the number of coating layers, almost zero-order release profiles with prolonged theophylline release periods were obtained.[87]

Cheema et al. coated SF onto an emodin-loaded liposome, which could help to tune emodin release by switching from swelling to diffusion-driven release. As a result, the approach not only preserved cell selectivity but also increased cellular uptake. As the intracellular retention period of emodin was lengthened, it resulted in improved overall therapeutic efficacy.[68]

CONCLUSION

Silk fibroin is a natural protein macromolecule that can be obtained from silkworms. It offers numerous advantages, including water and oxygen permeability, superior mechanical performance, and biocompatibility. SF, on the other hand, is resistant to the majority of solvents due to its hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic bonding. Only solvents capable of breaking these bonds, including peptide chain breakage, can dissolve SF. The most often used solvents for dissolving silk fibroin have been thoroughly explored here, along with their benefits and drawbacks. The various silk fibroin wound dressing materials were also described. Despite the rising number of research papers, commercially accessible silk fibroin wound dressings were not available until recently. Silk-based wound dressings are expected to enter the clinical application in the next years, with growing industry interest and investment due to their ability to demonstrate the required qualities.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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